

A propagation breakdown management model for the industrial internet of things

Eduardo Buetas*, Ismael Abad, Jose A. Cerrada, Carlos Cerrada

Department of Software and Systems Engineering, Universidad Nacional de Educacion a Distancia (UNED), 28040, Madrid, Spain

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ABSTRACT

The industry, in the near future, will undergo a great evolution in the automation systems and, at the same time should integrate the current running systems. These new in-use systems should be maintained and monitored with new tools and new processes. In this article, we propose a propagation breakdown management model to integrate any kind of control devices and any application that can exploit the maintenance information data. This model includes a proposal of this fault propagation model, based on MQTT (Message Queuing Telemetry Transport) protocol, capable of receiving the faults caused by the different systems, storing and distributing them to global systems.

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1. Introduction

The propagation breakdowns in the industrial world is a major issue for industrial productivity (Cachada et al., 2018). This implies that the failures produced are notified to the maintenance personnel of the industries, in the correct time and manner, so that they can be solved in the shortest time possible, minimizing the unproductive machines time, production lines or supply chains.

Until now, most of the controllers used in industrial automation were based on PLC (Programmable Logic Controller), but this was industry 3.0. Today, and much more in the coming years, with the unstoppable arrival of industry 4.0 we have more and more control elements (automation of machines, conveyors, Andon, Kanban, poka-yoke, warehouse management, etc.) based on non-PLC subsystems (Zhu et al., 2020), integrating the called CPSs (Cyber-physical Systems) (Cheng et al., 2018).

The IIoT is becoming more important in aiding asset management, introducing operational intelligence, remote monitoring and servicing, and predictive and corrective maintenance. Several initiatives are aimed to adopt the IIoT worldwide over the near future (Li et al., 2018).

The CPSs are composed of intelligent systems, storage systems, and production facilities capable of exchanging information autonomously, trigger actions and control each other indepen-

dently, according to the definition appeared in the report of the National Academy of Science and Engineering of Germany Kagermann Wahlster and Helbig (2013). These intelligent systems will generate their data that should be propagated to the higher systems of the industries (Yin et al., 2019):

Manufacturing Execution System (MES), Enterprise Resource Planning (ERP), breakdown management, quality management, etc. All these devices must coexist with the current automation elements based on PLCs and RTUs (Remote Terminal Unit). For this reason, it will be crucial to develop data propagation systems with communication protocols that could integrate past, current and future technologies (Sisinni et al., 2018).

The maintenance is widely recognized as an essential business function (de Jonge and Scarf, 2019). In this article, we propose a model that this system must follow to integrate the received data from new automation systems with older and running systems. In addition, there are new mobile devices (smartphones, tablets, phontabs, smart wears, etc.) used in the factories to help improving activities performance: work orders management, communication between participants of certain tasks, identification of machines and facilities, jobs reports, etc (Al-Najjar and Algabroun, 2018). These devices must also be integrated into this new framework, for example, as breakdowns notifications, as acknowledgement tool of them and as any other supports for the best development of corrective and preventive maintenance.

The best approach to this new challenge in communications will be the inclusion of common protocols in every element of the system. This solution avoids the inclusion of gateways that perform

* Corresponding author.

E-mail addresses: eduardo@buetassanjuan.name (E. Buetas), iabad@issi.uned.es (I. Abad), jcerrada@issi.uned.es (J.A. Cerrada), ccerrada@issi.uned.es (C. Cerrada).

the task of transferring/transforming the information between different network protocols of the participants.

The process of the propagation breakdowns is made up of different elements:

- Automation controllers: these systems are in charge of controlling and managing the machines and installations. All together are, usually, the main breakdowns generators.
- Breakdown management systems: devices that inform the corrective and preventive maintenance technicians immediately of the failures, warnings and incidents produced, and provide information for the correct and rapid resolution.
- Breakdown server: it is fundamental to manage structured and qualified information for the improvement of the systems, for the use of preventing breakdowns protocols and, for applying the breakdowns resolution actions. All the incidents related to the factory breakdowns should be registered: event time and data, and acknowledgement and resolution information.
- Sensors: in the new paradigm of the industry, connectable independent sensors begin to proliferate for the capture of environmental data; temperature, humidity, vibrations, etc.

The article is presented in three major sections before it is concluded. After this introduction section, management is surveyed across the industry. The next section presents the model proposal based on the breakdowns topics, the failures database, the propagation software, and the controller's management. The fourth section focuses on the example prototype and the model. This section also outlines the use of different technologies across the application of the propagation breakdowns management model. The fifth section includes conclusions details and describes the opened research trends about breakdown management.

2. Breakdown management

The e-maintenance paradigm more and more grows in the industrial maintenance systems (Guillén et al., 2016) trends. This suggests the increasingly important introduction of new technologies in the field of maintenance, as mobile devices for maintenance personnel, data acquisition with RFID technology, sensors implemented with SoC (System On Chip) systems to receive environment variables, data storage distribution in standardized formats and big data techniques application (Sahal et al., 2020) for later analysis.

There is a wide bibliography for the introduction of new approaches in maintenance management, as for example: augmented reality for the improvement of maintenance procedures (van Lopik et al., 2020), maintenance optimization based on simulated models (Huynh, 2020; Zhang et al., 2019), fault diagnosis methods based on artificial intelligence (Cao et al., 2018), deep reinforcement learning (Liu et al., 2020b) etc.

One of the next challenges of propagation breakdown systems will be the possibility of their interconnection with different systems based on different platforms.

There are articles about the interconnection of the new automation devices and data collection with the IoT's networks and their propagation to the higher servers through gateways, for example in Civerchia et al. (2017), Mahmoud and Xia (2017), Răileanu et al. (2018) and Kaed et al. (2018). But the inclusion of an intermediate device to translate the data of one type to another, to change the network transport, or to convert the protocol introduces a set of new elements that must be installed and maintained for its operation in the industrial environment. This is the main reason because in this article we propose a propagation breakdown system definition that can interconnect the existing devices in the current industry. We propose to use the same network and protocol

Fig. 1. Propagation Breakdown System Structure.

without adding any new device as a gateway for this maintenance purpose.

This is the main reason because in this article we propose a propagation breakdown system definition that can interconnect the existing devices in the current industry. We propose to use the same network and protocol without adding any new device as a gateway. At present, the majority of devices can connect to TCP networks, used as a common transport protocol to integrate the data into a propagation breakdown system.

3. Propagation breakdown management model

The model proposed in this article (Fig. 1) for the propagation of failures in the new industry paradigm must be able to make the necessary communications to interconnect the different elements of the system, defined in the previous section of this article. The model supports the new automation systems based on CPS control, connectable autonomous sensors, PLC systems and, hybrid and mixed subsystems.

This general model includes the following information flows:

- From automation controllers to breakdown server (F1). First, the breakdowns incidents are sent from the automation controllers to the breakdown server, and later on, the information about failures solutions.
- From breakdown server to breakdown management systems (F2). In the same way as in the previous item, the breakdowns data should be transmitted to the breakdown management systems.
- From breakdown management systems to breakdown server (F2). There is some information to translate and maintain as the acknowledge information or additional breakdowns data.
- From breakdown management systems to maintenance technician (F3). The filtered information about specific opened breakdowns is needed for infield technicians and it should be presented in their portable devices.
- From the maintenance technician to breakdown management systems (F3). The technicians introduce additional information about breakdowns that should be distributed.

Thus, to manage these communications between the elements of the system, a solution should be implemented in every participant. And to obtain optimal functioning, the protocol must be characterized by:

- Low program footprint that any light device can support it.
- High-capacity to manage large and heterogeneous devices with the same infrastructure.
- Easy configuration.
- Short start-up time.
- Transparent configuration incidence when adding elements.
- Easy routing.
- Quality Of Service (QoS) assurance.

Fig. 2. Publish/Subscribe Model for Breakdowns Propagation.

Fig. 3. Topic of Fault structure.

Between the communication alternatives models in the CPSs (Liu et al., 2018), we propose to employ a publish/subscribe approach (Fig. 2).

There are several publish-subscription protocols (Pattar et al., 2018) widely used. We propose to apply the MQTT (Message Queue Telemetry Transport) protocol because, in both fields, the IoT (Internet of Things) and in the IIoT (Industrial Internet of Things) is commonly applied. This protocol is used by main platforms like Amazon AWS (Pierleoni et al., 2020), IBM Watson IoT (Salhaoui et al., 2019) or Google IoT Cloud Core (Agarwal and Alam, 2018) to easy connect sensors in the specific IoT platforms. There are also several examples of industrial deployments of MQTT to solve light communications like Katsikeas et al. (2017), Ferrari et al. (2017) or Iglesias-Urkiá et al. (2017). The main advantage of MQTT (Liu et al., 2020a; Kevin, 2020; Sasaki and Yokotani, 2019) is that the TCP support can be applied to the most infield existing elements and a collection of heterogeneous resources in a publisher/subscriber network. MQTT is now an OASIS (Open Architecture System) standard and it has been approved as ISO standard, called ISO/IEC 20922 from June 2016. The protocol continues the evolution, the latest published version is 5.0 (OASIS 2018).

3.1. Breakdowns topics

The messages in the model are published and subscribed through nodes that are hierarchically organized in topics. The main two topics are "Faults" and "Information".

The message "Faults", includes all the system failures details (Fig. 3). This structure is organized in the following seven levels:

- Area: this first subdivision serves to organize the breakdowns depending on factory areas or topological places, for example in automotive production:
 - Body-shop: toy tabbing, sheet-metal body, spot-welds.
 - Paint-shop: KTL (cataphoresis), prime, base coat, clear coat, wiping.
 - Trim-chassis-final and engine, transmission and tires mounted into.

Fig. 4. Topic of Information structure.

- Subarea: following the example of the automotive factory, it is common for maintenance teams to be divided by the functionality of the facilities, which could correspond to the subareas defined within each area:
 - Conveyors: floor, power & free, EMS/EHB, etc.
 - Machines: Robot stations, spot welding stations, paint shop workstations.
 - Infrastructure: Andon quality, Andon material, Poka-Yoke, . . .
- Equipment: each of the equipment controlled by a single automation system is defined as an equipment node; continuing with our example of an automotive factory, equipment would be a group of conveyors that are controlled by a single control system, a concrete machine, a robotic welding cell, etc.
- Zone: every equipment can be divided into one or several zones, for example, it is common for a conveyor to have the elements divided by emergency zones, or by the level of installation. In general, the subdivision into resource zones of a device is carried out for the quick localization of an element within the systems controlled by this equipment.
- Element: in this level, it is introduced the name of the element that has produced the fault. An element could be, inside a conveyor, one of the tables that compose it (lifters, rotating tables, rollers tables, etc.), or inside a robotized cell, a specific robot or a clamp.
- Fault description: as the last topic level, we propose to have the fault name produced in the element, it should be a descriptive name of the fault. Using the previous example, the roller table (i.e. RT1) breakdowns could be:
 - Transit time to end-sensor (i.e. B1) exceeded.
 - Motor (i.e. M1) fault.
 - Detection end-sensor (i.e. B1) out of time cycle.
 - Etc.

All these organizational subdivisions of each breakdown must be completed for the proper function of our model. If there is a level that does not have subdivisions, a single child should be created as a mandatory restriction.

The descriptions of these levels must be significant for the location and understanding of the produced faults.

The second main topic managed in the model is "Information". We use a message "Information" that includes extra information. In this message, there is a child level for each of the fault reception equipment, which has the name of this equipment. Each of the levels referenced to the failure reception equipment includes four child elements (Fig. 4). These allow to store the information that can be published about equipment:

- Message: Short text briefly describing the fault.
- Description: Text that describes the fault in detail.
- Action: Recommended action to solve the fault.

Fig. 5. DBMS main entities.

- Priority: Fault resolution priority, being a classification in integers, the highest priority being the value 0.

3.2. Structured failures database

The database management system (DBMS) contains the system database with the breakdowns list, with all its data, and store the incidents related to each failure, occurrences, and resolutions of each of them, acknowledgement by the corrective maintenance personnel, etc. These data must be stored for the generation of breakdowns analysis reports, which help to plan preventive maintenance or to modify the action protocols of maintenance personnel. A summary diagram is shown in Fig. 5.

3.3. Propagation software

This software is responsible for the publications and subscriptions that the server must perform for the correct system functioning. This software subscribes to the topic "Faults/#" receiving all the messages whose topic begins with "Faults".

All timestamp including in the database are obtained in the server because for these data the communication time is considered negligible.

When it receives a message type "1", it reads about the topic through which the message arrives with the fields that identify a unique fault: area, subarea, equipment, zone, element and

fault description. With these data, it includes this incidence in the database of the system as "Open Fault", including the instant timestamp in which the fault is produced.

At that moment of receiving a message of type "2-name of the sending team", as in the previous case, it reads the information for the unique identification of the breakdown topic that arrives. The system adds the opened fault to the database with the timestamp of the instant of acknowledgement, as well as the maintenance technician who has made the reception acknowledgement.

Finally, upon receiving a message of type "3-type of information requested", it triggers the publication of the required information. This software publishes this specific information of a breakdown requested by a "Fault Reception Team", consulting the information in the database, uniquely identifying the failure, based on the information obtained from the topic. It generates a topic composed of the following way "Information/ Name of the equipment that has requested the information/ Type of information" and in the content of the message it sends the information required by the petitioner of this.

3.4. Automation controllers

These systems only act as messages publishers in the system without being subscribed to any node. They are configured with the area and subarea where they are located, the name of the equip-

Fig. 6. Paint-shop Conveyors Plant.

ment and with its different zones and elements within each zone, as well as the description of each element faults.

When a fault occurs, the system builds the chain corresponding to the topic:

"Faults/Area/Subarea/Equipment/Zone/Element/Fault Descriptions"

And it sends a message "1" to the system. When the fault is solved, it sends a message "0" to the system with the same topic.

When the controller is connected to the broker, a special message is sent to inform the propagation faults software and the subscribers of this controller that it is connected. This message has the content "0" in the topic:

"Faults/Area/Subarea/Equipment/Mqtt/Mqtt/Connection"

Being its zone, element and name, constants values for all controllers.

Also, when the installation broker detects the disconnection of one of this equipment, it sends a message "1" with the same previous topic. This special fault is configured in all the controllers to allow the server to know in every moment which controllers have lost the connection with the server. Hence, they are not sending faults to the system.

When a controller disconnects from the system, the connection flag of the MQTT protocol "will", defined for this convenience, will be used as protocol standard to send this information.

3.5. Alarm reception equipment

These specific devices subscribe to two different topics. The first topic is subscribed to the upper message of the area that a maintenance technician is in charge. For example, a maintenance specialist technician who must deal with the asset type "conveyors" is subscribed

"Faults/Paint-shop/Conveyors/#"

This equipment shows a list of faults. When a message "1" of a fault is received, the fault information is shown as unacknowledged (red colour) in the faults list. When the fault is acknowledged, by the same team, or by another, a fault message "2-name of the acknowledging team" is received, with the referred information failure obtained uniquely by the topic. The fault is searched in the list and its status and colour are changed, turning it as acknowledged but not solved (yellow colour).

When the equipment receives a message "0" about a fault, the user by configuration can maintain the fault in the list until a manual deletion. In this situation, it remains in the faults list as acknowledged and resolved (green colour) or it disappears immediately.

The user may request additional information on a specific breakdown as mentioned in the topic structure section. For this purpose, the team sends a message, with the same topic about the fault has been received, to request the supplementary information about it, with one of the following messages:

- "3-message"
- "3-description"
- "3-act"
- "3-priority"
- "3-all"

When this happens, the team is waiting for the information with its second MQTT topic subscriber:

"Information/Team Name/#"

The topic is received in this subscription with all the additional information that is sent by the server of the installation.

Furthermore, to make the fault acknowledgement, these devices send a message "2-team name" with the same topic received in the fault creation. This equipment must be portable equipment that maintenance technicians can carry over their workday, such as smartphones, tablets, tablets-pc, etc. They should produce the corresponding warnings when an incident appears in the system: sound warnings, vibrations, notifications, etc.

3.6. Propagation breakdowns example

This section proposes an application example of the propagation breakdown management model described in the previous chapter. A typical Functional Group (i.e. FG1) in the Paint-shop Conveyors Plant could be represented with Fig. 6:

Breakdowns Description. In FG1, it appears a breakdown in Transit Time B1 in the element Roller Conveyor 1 (RT1) that is located in Zone 1 of this functional group. Because of this failure, the FG1 controller automatically publishes a message "1" on the corresponding topic:

"Faults/Paint-shop/Conveyors/FG1/Zone 1/RT1/Time Transit B1"

This message is received by the broker who controls the propagation breakdowns and sent by the broker to all the subscribers who are hierarchically subscribed to it.

In this example, we suppose the propagation breakdowns software and all breakdowns receptors that are assigned to the area are subscribed. In a real environment, the maintenance teams that oversee the corrective maintenance of the paint-shop conveyors would be subscribed to all the messages below the hierarchy, subscribing to:

"Faults/Paint-shop/Conveyors/#"

The propagation breakdowns software, when receiving this message realizes an annotation in the system database with the fault creation and the timestamp with the instant in which the fault has appeared. And the alarm reception equipment subscribed should inform the maintenance technician about the produced fault.

Acknowledge Breakdown Reception. The maintenance technician assigned to the smartphone receiver 1 acknowledges the notification. The smartphone 1 answers the same topic for which the fault has been received with a message "2-Smartphone 1" that is received by the broker and it is resent to all the subscribers, which are the same ones that have received the first notification failure.

The propagation breakdowns software includes in the breakdown record the acknowledgement timestamp and the technician

associated with the smartphone alarm receptor equipment 1, who has accused the fault. Also, the other alarm receiving equipment receives the breakdown acknowledgement with the breakdown status change to "Acknowledged".

Breakdown Additional Information Demand. The maintenance technician with the smartphone receiver 2 requires extra information about the breakdown recommended action. The alarm reception equipment 2 sends a message "3-action" using the same topic received with the breakdown. This message is received by the broker and re-sent to all the subscribers of the failure. In this situation, the message of type "3" is discarded by the Alarm Receptions Equipment.

The propagation breakdowns software searches in the database for the required information and sends this information as the content of a message sent to the topic:

"Information/Smartphone 2/action"

This message is received by the broker and sent to the subscribers to this topic, which in this example is only the smartphone 2, and shows it to the technician who requested the information.

Breakdown Solution. When the breakdown in FG1 is solved and disappears, automatically the automation controller in this functional group publishes a message "0" with the same topic posted in the initial breakdown message. And it re-sends it to all the subscribed equipment: in this example, they are both the propagation breakdowns software and the alarm reception equipment.

The propagation breakdowns software moves the breakdown from the live breakdowns table to the solved breakdowns table, adding the instant timestamp in which the fault was solved.

4. Model implementation and prototype

This section describes the model implementation for the experimental validation of the proposed solution in the previous sections. This implementation develops a propagation breakdown management software, which contains a DBMS with the system database, the MQTT broker and the specific software for the propagation breakdowns.

This prototype includes three fault generators, one based on a PLC, another based on an embedded micro-PC and another based on a micro-controller. These implementations try to demonstrate the versatility of the system, being able to manage a wide range of current and future automation controllers.

These controllers, when it detects a fault, for example, if the control of a roller table detects a movement time, greater than the maximum transit time, it sends the corresponding fault message.

The necessary software for the breakdowns receiver has been developed as an Android app.

All code used to test this system is accessible in the public repository:

<https://anonymous.4open.science/r/13687bfd-7f5d-4a67-9bc9-b4ee410b2225/>.

4.1. Server prototype

The prototyping propagation breakdown server developed uses a machine with an Ubuntu Server 16.0.4 as operating system, Mosquitto as MQTT broker and PostgreSQL as database server, where the database described in Fig. 5 has been created.

This prototype system is neither redundant nor balanced because it is not necessary for demonstration purposes. In a real environment and considering the importance of 24×7 availability of this kind of system, the use of several redundant servers should be considered for the execution of this software.

For the tests carried out in this article, we used the following example registered (Tables 1, 2 and 3) faults.

We have developed the software with two MQTT clients. First of them subscribes to a general topic: "Faults/#" to receive all the messages related to the system breakdowns. And the second one is used to publish additional information about the faults at the request of Alarm Reception Equipment.

When the client subscribed to "Faults/#" receives a message, the first check we do is to parse the associated topic. This exam verifies that the message has the seven required components that every topic must-have. Once this is done, and knowing that the topic has the required seven parts, the program breaks them down into its seven components and reads all the data of the fault from the database.

4.2. Controllers examples

The developed automation controllers for the prototype publish the appearance and disappearance of faults in the system. When the fault appears or disappears, these controllers publish an MQTT message naming uniquely the fault. The data sent to the broker in the topic is "1" when the fault appears and "0" when it disappears.

In addition to the installation faults, each automation controller manages a fault connection error of himself with the MQTT broker. This is implemented with a fault that is created with the "Mqtt" zone and with the "Mqtt" element, and the fault name is "Connection". When the controller makes a successful connection to the broker, an initial message is sent with the topic: "Faults/Area/Subarea/Equipment/Mqtt/Mqtt/Connection" and with the content of the message equal to "0".

In this connection, the "willTopic" of the connection is: "Faults/Area/Subarea/Equipment/Mqtt/Mqtt/Connection" and the "willMessage" is set equal to "1". With this configuration, we get that when the installation broker detects a disconnection of this publisher, it sends the failed connection message to the different subscribers.

Fig. 7. Breakdowns List with acknowledgement.

Table 1
Breakdowns PLC prototype; Area: Paint; Subarea: Conveyor; Equipment: FG1.

Zone	Elem.	Fault	Message	Description
Level 0	RT1	Transit Time B1	The transit time for arrival at B1 has been exceeded	An error occurs when the transit time between the starting skid to the end detector exceeds a given time
Level 1	TT2	Thermal Motor	There has been a trigger thermal trip protection of a motor	The motor thermal protection has been triggered by an overvoltage produced in the motor
Mqtt	Mqtt	Connection	A connection error has occurred	The MQTT client equipment has been disconnected from the broker, the equipment will not send faults until it is reconnected.

Table 2
Breakdowns micro-PC prototype; Area: Paint; Subarea: Machines; Equipment: Booth1.

Zone	Elem.	Fault	Message	Description
Zone 1	Static 1	Fault nozzle 5	Nozzle controller 5 has given a fail	High voltage or pressure control failure in nozzle controller number 5
Mqtt	Mqtt	Connection	A connection error has occurred	The MQTT client equipment has been disconnected from the broker, the equipment will not send faults until it is reconnected.

Table 3
Breakdowns micro-controller prototype; Area: Weld; Subarea: Conveyors; Equipment: FG3.

Zone	Elem.	Fault	Message	Description
Level 0	RT1	Cycle Fault B1	Detect B1 detector out of cycle	Detector B1 has activated in a stage that it must be deactivated
Mqtt	Mqtt	Connection	A connection error has occurred	The MQTT client equipment has been disconnected from the broker, the equipment will not send faults until it is reconnected.

Fig. 8. Messages Exchanges: Appears breakdown and acknowledge breakdown.

These publishers may be based on multiple platforms. As MQTT is a light protocol, a publisher of this protocol can be integrated into platforms with few resources. For example, for the prototype of our system, we built three cases of automation controllers, all with QoS 2:

- PLC. Specifically in a Siemens PLC S7-1211C.
- Micro PC. Particularly with a Raspberry Pi 3 B + Model.
- Micro-controller. Using an Arduino MKR 1000 Model with Wifi Module.

This selection covers exemplars for possible automation systems, and is, a good test to show the MQTT protocol flexibility in different platforms.

4.3. Breakdowns client receivers

The corrective maintenance technicians carry the mobile equipment where the system notifies them the faults produced in the controlled areas. These teams are subscribed to the topics that are in the area or subarea for which they are responsible.

For the prototype developed in this article, an Android application is used as a client breakdowns receiver. When a fault occurs in one of these topics to which the app is subscribed, these devices automatically receive the message with the information of the area, sub-area, equipment, zone, element and fault description. These alarms are displayed on the breakdowns list in the app main screen, together with the timestamp when the messages were received. All the faults are shown by order of appearance: the newest are displayed first.

If the carrier of this equipment takes charge of solving the fault, he should acknowledge the message and the system stores the acknowledgement time and the technician. To do this, the technician clicks on the fault to deal with, and one screen appears where he can acknowledge the fault and request more information about it. By clicking on the "Ack" button, the acknowledgement is sent to the server and to all the other fault reception devices that are subscribed to the topic of this breakdown. The system informs them that this fault has already been taken care of by a user of the system (Fig. 7).

From the same screen used to acknowledge the faults, there is also an option to request additional information about the selected

Fig. 9. Messages Exchanges: Disappears breakdown and demand additional information.

Breakdown Management System Sends Information

Fig. 10. Messages Exchanges: Breakdown management system sends information.

breakdown. This option sends a message with the same fault topic that has been received. The server re-sends the request with the required information to the topic:

"Information/Name of equipment/Type of Information"

4.4. Sample message exchange

In the following figures (Figs. 8, 9, and 10) can see the different messages exchanged in the process of appearance, disappearance, acknowledgement and request for information for a breakdown.

5. Conclusions and future works

5.1. Conclusions

In this article, we have exposed the current and future state of the industrial communications for the propagation breakdown management. This situation exists and it will be increased, with the introduction of the new industrial control systems in the industry 4.0 environment. The current control systems, usually controlled by PLC systems and the new ones, that will be controlled by other types of control systems, will propagate information to the upper industrial control systems, such as breakdowns manager systems, production control systems, MESS, ERPs, etc. Most of the current proposals start with the premise that to make these communications possible, it is necessary to include gateways to connect between the different network layers in the industrial control systems and the upper management servers of manufacture.

This paper aims to demonstrate that there is a way to communicate, current and future industrial automation systems. It is possible using existing protocols to make communication without employ specific gateways. This is feasible because most of the current industrial control systems and those used in industry 4.0 have TCP communication capabilities. So by using a light protocol, which uses TCP transport protocol, we can integrate all the controllers in a network for direct communication between them.

With this objective, in this work, we have proposed a general software architecture to support a propagation breakdown management system. Also, as an example to show the proposal demonstration, we have developed a prototype which includes automation controllers using three different types of devices and using the MQTT protocol without the inclusion of any gateway.

5.2. Future trends

There are several open research topics based on this work. Some issues that remain open in the development of this article are, for example, the security of communications, the communication network configuration or the possibility of server redundancy.

The communications security using the MQTT protocol must be properly insured to avoid undesirable damages. MQTT standard OASIS (2018) strongly recommend implementing MQTT over TLS Dierks and Rescorla (2008), but in constrained resources devices it is not possible. We must work with the use of encryption methods for the propagation of breakdowns messages. Although we can assume safe factories communication networks, we must consider an in-depth security strategy, making these communications

through secure protocols that prevent a man-in-the-middle attack and applying physical-layer security technology Pan et al. (2018) to avoid security flaws in our system.

The system described in this article includes a very easy configuration and very short operator instructions to include new fault generators. However, the problem of configuring the network elements where the system messages travel through is not solved yet. The development process of an integrated MQTT broker in the propagation breakdowns software will be a new research line to take into account for future works. In this way, it would be possible to have total control about the broker operations, including more aspects like the security and the balancing working that an industrial system of these characteristics requires.

Finally, it would be necessary to search for an automatic code generator for the code modules for MQTT communications, and the failure lists of each automation system to be imported into the system database.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Eduardo Buetas: Conceptualization, Methodology, Software, Investigation, Writing - original draft, Writing - review & editing. **Ismael Abad:** Conceptualization, Methodology, Investigation, Writing - original draft, Writing - review & editing. **Jose A. Cerrada:** Funding acquisition, Validation. **Carlos Cerrada:** Funding acquisition, Validation.

Declaration of Competing Interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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